

V (ПЯТАЯ)

**МЕЖДУНАРОДНАЯ НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКАЯ
КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ**

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ИНДЕКСАЦИЯ

EXPLORE

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НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ КОНФЕРЕНЦИИ

 **НАУЧНЫЕ
ТЕХНОЛОГИИ
ПЕДАГОГИКА
ПСИХОЛОГИЯ
ФИЛОСОФИЯ
ИСТОРИЯ**

 **ИНФОРМАТИКА
ТЕХНИЧЕСКИЕ
НАУКИ
МАТЕМАТИЧЕСКИЙ
АНАЛИЗ**

 **ЭКОНОМИКА
ФИНАНСЫ**

Введение

В сборнике материалов конференции, посвященных роли науки, образования и производства в эпоху глобализации, актуальным проблемам взаимодействия этих процессов, отзываю об их решениях, были представлены зрелые специалисты отрасли.

Кроме того, представлены исследования на научно-практическую тему, проводимые в области экономики, точных наук, естественных и социально-гуманитарных наук в период глобализации, представлена информация в научно-практической сфере, которая включает в себя новейшие инновационные технологии в сферах производства.

Можно утверждать, что этот сборник является одним из специфических перекрестков современных мыслей и инновационных идей в мире науки. В этой научно-практической конференции приняли активное участие профессора и научные сотрудники, занимающиеся научными исследованиями в Узбекистане и зарубежных странах. Значительный вклад в повышение позиций научно-практической конференции внесли профессора и преподаватели отечественных и зарубежных высших учебных заведений.

Профессора и преподаватели зарубежных высших учебных заведений, активно участвовавшие в работе конференции, внесли достойный вклад в высокий уровень взаимодействия с учеными нашей страны. Процессы международного сотрудничества с зарубежными странами и обмена с ними в области науки в эпоху глобализации оказывают положительное влияние на развитие высшего образования, сфер науки и производства. Материалы этой конференции особенны тем, что включают в себя широкий спектр исследований, от теоретических разработок до практических решений, демонстрирующих разнообразие подходов и направлений в этой области.

В заключение следует отметить, что данная научно-практическая конференция станет очень полезным собранием для всех, кто интересуется современными исследованиями в области дальнейшего развития высшего образования, науки, воспитательной работы и производства в эпоху глобализации. Авторы несут ответственность за содержание и качество статей и тезисов, включенных в сборник.

FACTORS FOR DEVELOPING READING CULTURE IN PRIMARY EDUCATION THROUGH ACTS

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The adoption of Resolution No. PQ-3180 by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 8, 2017, "On Improving the Activities of the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan," brought the educational process in the general secondary education system to a qualitatively new level. In accordance with this resolution, the general secondary education system is to be organized on the basis of ongoing socio-economic reforms in the country, the advanced experiences of developed foreign countries, and modern information and communication technologies. Ensuring the continuity of vocational guidance for students in primary education, as well as mastering new forms of modern information technologies and vocational guidance to ensure their employment, is of great importance for the socio-economic development of our country.

The rapid development of the world economy and the acceleration of progress are leading to the improvement of the international labor market and the emergence of a growing number of new professions. The vocational guidance system in the international arena has a dual character: it develops according to certain general ideas and criteria, and is also characterized by the improvement of the national system of vocational guidance in accordance with the unique level of development of each country.

In guiding primary school students toward a profession, reading culture should be considered the primary criterion for developing the following qualities in students:

In particular:

- Developing noble qualities in young students such as modesty, decency, respect for parents, esteem for elders, and kindness toward the younger generation;
- Forming thorough knowledge of the heritage of our great ancestors, being raised worthy of them, and cultivating an incomparable respect for the values and traditions that have come down to us;
- Making students understand that personal development and spirituality are among the most important factors in social society;
- Instilling in their consciousness the unique characteristics of human virtues;

- Helping them understand that qualities such as patriotism, compassion, faith, and dedication are among the most fundamental factors in societal progress;
- Developing in young people the skills of independent and creative thinking, filtering information, and analytical reasoning;
- Cultivating a deep sense of the essence of national and spiritual values reflected in historical works: love for the homeland, loyalty to the fatherland, and a sense of belonging to it;
- Directing the positive qualities present in literary heroes — dedication, peacefulness, wisdom, psychological and spiritual potential — toward purposeful goals;
- By comparing events in works with real-life situations of the student, developing qualities of politeness, honesty, and conscientiousness in daily activities;
- Caring about the future and independence of our Homeland, understanding and protecting the dignity and honor of one's people, working with noble intentions and dedicating one's talents and all available means to the future of our country.

The use of information and communication technology tools in the continuing education system not only enhances reading culture but also improves the quality and effectiveness of education through the modernization of the teaching and upbringing process. Thus, information is a sign that prompts the expression of attitudes toward reality by perceiving external influences and analyzing and synthesizing them through internal experiences. With the help of this sign, students strive to understand the objects, phenomena, and the content and essence of the works they have read, compare them, and comprehend their similarities and differences. Developing reading culture in students through information and communication technologies serves as a foundation for generating new judgments. These appear as new signs, enriching the content of concepts and transforming into knowledge. A student who possesses such information develops creative thinking and the capacity for new thought; as a result, the student gains the ability to discover, invent, and take initiative.

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